

The Influence of Democratic Leadership on Employee Performance at The Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community (DP3AM) Of Binjai City

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of Democratic Leadership on Employee Performance in the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services in Binjai City. This research was carried out at the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection, Binjai City. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 61 employees of the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Department of Binjai City. The sampling technique in this research uses saturated samples so that the entire population will be a sample of 61 people. The research results show that Democratic Leadership has a significant influence on Employee Performance as shown by the T-Statistic value of $3,782 > 1.670$ and the P Value of $0.003 < 0.05$. The adjusted R Square value is 0.257 or 25.70%, which means that democratic leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 74.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. This shows that improvements in Democratic Leadership will be able to improve the performance of employees of the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City.

Keywords: Democratic Leadership; Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is basically a description of the employee's ability to handle each job, where the level of employee performance can be assessed from the employee's ability to produce work that meets predetermined standards. Meanwhile, low employee performance is caused by several factors such as: indiscipline at work, late completion of tasks and low responsibility for work, so that the work results obtained are not optimal, because they do not meet the expected standards/targets, resulting in low performance. employees will influence the quality of service to the community. Therefore, it is expected that every employee has competence.

Each government organization definitely has different goals from one government organization to another. In achieving this goal, many various factors are involved in this achievement. In this case, the important influencing factor is human resources. Apart from that, every government organization also needs energy and thoughts that come from human resources. HR's energy and thoughts must be able to show their work performance. Employee performance is very much needed in carrying out work activities. Government organizations usually have good and bad employee performance. All of these things depend on each individual employee. Every government organization certainly wants to get good employee performance in each respective field. Employee performance is

expected to produce good quality work and the amount of work that meets standards (Wiandari & Gede, 2017).

Research conducted by (Kesuma & Syamsuddin, 2019) states that there is an influence of motivation on employee performance. Hypothesis testing results show that there is no influence of Democratic leadership style on employee performance. This research is supported by (Hidayah, 2021) who says that individual characteristics and leadership style influence performance, meaning that every individual characteristic and good leadership style will improve a person's performance. Furthermore, research conducted by (Aktarina, 2015) shows that individual characteristics have a significant influence on work motivation and employee performance. Research conducted by (Senen et al., 2021) states that leadership style has a significant effect on work motivation.

Leadership is the ability to influence a group towards achieving a set vision or goal. The source of this influence can be formal, as is the case with managerial rank within the organization (Robbins et al., 2017). Modern leadership views leaders as individuals who inspire their followers through words, ideas and behavior (Robbins et al., 2017). Leaders function to inspire their followers to go beyond the employees' own self-interest and have the ability to have a deep influence. They work collaboratively to meet their needs and communicate the organization's vision and mission to employees. So it can have implications and have a significant influence on employee performance (Eliyana et al., 2019).

The phenomenon seen in the Department of Village Community Empowerment, Women and Child Protection in Binjai City in improving the performance of women's empowerment is not as expected, this is proven by the problems that occur in the field, namely low employee competence seen from the behavior of employees who are irresponsible and work, such as many employees arriving late, good attendance but not carrying out their work optimally, completing work not on time and providing unsatisfactory service.

From the description of the performance of the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) employees, it can be seen that efforts need to be made to find approaches that can improve the performance of Binjai City DP3AM employees. The approach that is considered appropriate for increasing the empowerment of women of Binjai City DP3AM employees is an approach to improving the quality of human resources, namely looking at factors that can influence employee performance such as competence, job training, employee job satisfaction levels, job stress, company work cultures. give to employees, (Wannebo & Ridlwan Muttaqin, 2023).

Leadership style is the behavior or method chosen and used by a leader to influence the thoughts, feelings, attitudes and behavior of members and subordinates. Leadership style is a person's characteristic of influencing other people or organizations, so that other people are willing and able to move and emulate their personal attitudes and character towards achieving goals (Ali et al., 2015).

Democratic leadership style is the ability to influence other people to cooperate in achieving the goals that have been set by means of various activities that will be carried out jointly between the leader and subordinates (Susanti, 2015).

According to (Susanti, 2015), the indicators for measuring democratic leadership style are:

1. Ability to encourage subordinates to use their cognitive and reasoning powers in solving various problems faced;
2. Encourage the use of innovation and creativity in carrying out tasks;
3. Leaders and subordinates are both involved in decision making or problem solving;
4. The relationship between leaders and subordinates is well established.

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures. , criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable in the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

1. Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
2. Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.
3. Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
4. Cooperate with other people at work.

The aim of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of Democratic Leadership on the Performance of Employees of the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection (DP3AM) Department of Binjai City. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image,

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) Binjai City. The time this research was carried out was from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher

to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees in the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community (DP3AM) in Binjai City, totaling 61 people.

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 61 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Transformational Leadership

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely democratic leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Democratic Leadership	61	1.75	5.00	4.0410	,74047
Performance	61	2.00	5.00	4.2869	,81245
Valid N (listwise)	61				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the democratic leadership and performance of employees at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) as above average, with mean scores of 4,041 and 4,286 respectively on a 1- scale. 5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.7404 for democratic leadership and 0.8124 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables. .

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for the Democratic Leadership Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KD1	0.630 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KD2	0.828 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KD3	0.693 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KD4	0.681 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the democratic leadership variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.252 with a significance value of 0.00 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the democratic leadership variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.808 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.851 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.709 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.710 > 0.252	0.00 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.252 with a significance value of

0.00 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018)

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Democratic leadership	0.672	4
Employee Performance	0.770	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the democratic leadership and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	1 (Constant)	15,350	2,335		
Democratic Leadership	,111	,142	,101	3,782	,003

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 6, the regression equation $Y = 15.350 + 0.111X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 15,350 means that if there is no democratic leadership, then there is an employee performance of 15,350 points. The regression coefficient for democratic leadership is 0.111, meaning that democratic leadership influences an increase in employee performance by 0.111 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,101a	,010	,257	3,260

a. Predictors: (Constant), Democratic Leadership

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.257 or 25.70%, which means that democratic leadership has a moderate influence on employee performance, while the remaining 74.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of democratic leadership on the performance of employees at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City

Ha: There is an influence of democratic leadership on the performance of employees at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15,350	2,335		6,575	,000
	Democratic Leadership	,111	,142	,101	3,782	,003

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 3.782 > t table 1,670, with a significance value of 0.003 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between democratic leadership on employee performance at the Women's Empowerment Service. , Protection of Children and the Community of Binjai City.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Democratic Leadership on the Performance of Employees of the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City, these findings are in line with research results (Ahmad

Paskha Aprilia Sitio, 2023) which show that the Influence of Democratic Leadership on Employee Performance. The results of hypothesis testing show that the t-value The calculation for the variable Democratic Leadership Style on Employee Performance is 3.782 and the p-value (Sig.) is 0.003. Because the t-calculated value is greater than the ttable value ($3.782 > 1.670$) and the significance value is $0.003 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that Democratic Leadership Style has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that Democratic Leadership (interpersonal relationships) has a positive and significant influence on the performance of employees at the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and the Community of Binjai City. This result is supported by the calculated t value of $3.782 > t$ table 1,670, with a significance value of $0.003 < 0.05$ which shows that if Democratic Leadership is improved, employee performance will increase.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.257 or 25.70%, which means that democratic leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 74.30% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the research results, discussions and conclusions obtained, the following suggestions can be given:

- a. Based on the research results, it is known that the democratic leadership and performance variables need to be maintained and improved. Therefore, the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Affairs in Binjai City should improve interpersonal relations with employees. Providing space for opinions to employees will also increase democratic voice so that having a space for democratic voice is expected to improve employee performance.
- b. So that future researchers can develop this research by developing a research model involving conditional variables as moderating variables so they can find out variables that strengthen or weaken employee performance.

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